

FACILITATING REFLECTION ON CLIMATE CHANGE USING INTERACTIVE SONIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the possibility of using musical soundscapes to facilitate reflection on the impacts of climate change. By sonifying historic and future climate data, an interactive timeline was created where the user can explore a soundscape changing in time. A prototype was developed and tested in a user study with 15 participants. Results indicate that the prototype successfully elicits the emotions that it was designed to communicate and that it does influence the participants' reflections. However, it remains uncertain how much the prototype actually helped them while reflecting.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this study, the idea of facilitating reflection on the impacts of climate change was used as the foundation for creating a prototype¹ that sonifies underlying climate data as a part of an interactive, musical soundscape experience. The hope for the prototype was that it would allow listeners to immerse themselves emotionally in a space that implicitly helps them think deeper thoughts about the state of the planet without alarming them with discomfiting facts or numbers. The soundscape was created using SuperCollider², where the graphical interface was kept minimalistic and where previous work within sonification and sound interaction design was used to guide the design choices of the mappings and overall aesthetics. Finally, a user study with 15 participants was conducted to evaluate the intuitiveness of the mapping between physical and auditory dimension, the feelings communicated by the design and the prototype's ability of facilitating reflection.

As humans, a substantial part of our behavior is determined by our values. Research based on Schwartz's model of 10 universal, dynamic and interrelated value types [1], suggests that values can predict an individual's attitude towards the environment, where the two value types associated with sustainable behavior are called universalism and benevolence [2]. Together, they form the category called *self-transcending* (ST) values which include values such as honesty, unity with nature and social justice. Contrarily, the category that is negatively correlated with sustainable behavior is called *self-enhancing* (SE) values and it contains the value types: power, achievement and hedonism. These types include values such as wealth, social power and being successful.

In sustainable human-computer interaction (HCI) research, one approach within pro-environmental persuasive design involves reinforcing ST values, since activating a value through manipulation boosts behaviors related to it (which is used in e.g. consumer

marketing) and this is the rationale behind developing technologies that target values [3]. There are a magnitude of possible approaches to this, but five patterns are discussed in particular by Knowles and colleagues [3]. The pattern called *facilitating reflection* is based on the fact that information which is perceived as threatening and urgent often – counterintuitively – makes people less likely to adopt sustainable behavior changes. Thus, they propose that designs should instead focus on giving individuals the opportunity to reflect and remind themselves about why the environment is important to them and the things they care about.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1. Sustainable HCI

In the intersection of sustainability and HCI lies the question of how technology can contribute towards sustained pro-environmental behavior. Within HCI, persuasive design explores the way design patterns can influence and change behavior. The link between these two fields and value types are at the core of the research by Knowles and colleagues [3, 4], in which they present five patterns of persuasion for sustainability – each with their corresponding anti-pattern. These are: *broad self-transcendence*, *consistency*, *designing to the value*, *facilitating reflection* and *measuring impact ripples*. In short, they suggest that the number of self-transcending values in a technology should outweigh the number of self-enhancing values, and do so with a consistent, long-term message. Also, designs should focus on fostering environmental concern, instead of changing behaviors, and the systemic effects should also be measured instead of solely the direct effects.

The anti-pattern that they call *provide information* is based on the belief that the more information a person has about climate change, or their unsustainable lifestyle, the more likely they are to change their behavior. On the contrary, providing this information often increases resistance to change or feelings of guilt which – together with the fact that people generally rank ST values as more important than SE values – constitute the motivation behind creating designs that *facilitate reflection* instead. This pattern encourages the development of tools that remind people about their preference of ST values by allowing them to contemplate the importance of protecting the environment [3].

2.2. Aesthetics and Emotions in Music and Interaction

The line between music and sonification can be blurry since musical elements and practices, e.g. tonality and adjusting tempo, are often used to facilitate the interpretation of a sonification. On the topic of where one draws that line, Vickers questions whether

¹Video Demonstration: <https://shorturl.at/gzB09>

²<https://supercollider.github.io/>

Data Type	Source
GHP (Global Human Population)	1850–2100: Our World in Data
GCP (Global Cattle Population)	1900–2010: Our World in Data 2020–2100: FAO
GLU (Global Land Use)	1850–2100: Our World in Data
GSFC (Global Synthetic Fertilizer Consumption)	1900–1950 Blanco, 2011 1960–2010: Our World in Data 2020–2050: Blanco, 2011
GMSL (Global Mean Sea Level Rise))	1850–2020: Our World in Data 2030–2050: NOAA
GMSTI (Global Mean Surface Temperature Increase)	1850–2020: Our World in Data 2030–2100: IPCC, AR5
CO ₂ , CH ₄ and N ₂ O Levels	1850–2100: IPCC, AR5

Table 1: Climate data sources.

it is meaningful to draw a clear-cut distinction and proposes instead a continuum between the two concepts. The bottom-line is that sonification can, and perhaps should, draw inspiration from musical aesthetics to improve the way sonification conveys information [5].

Bresin and Friberg [6] explored the emotional carrying abilities of musical performance according to certain musical variables (e.g. tempo, loudness). Using the emotional 2D-space of activity and valence proposed by Juslin and Timmers [7], the results provided ranges and characteristic values of musical variables when rendering specific emotional qualities, e.g. fast tempo is typical for more active emotions, such as anger or happiness, while a slow tempo is usually associated to low activity emotions, such as sadness or tenderness. These results can be used as means for eliciting certain emotions on the behalf of the listener.

3. METHOD

3.1. Data Collection

The data used for the sonification were compiled from multiple sources, as per Table 1. In the following text the acronyms presented in Tables 1 and 2 will be used when referring to data types. When complete historical or future data were lacking, the missing data points were linearly extra- or interpolated. For the greenhouse gasses (CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O), four data points were collected per decade: one value for each of the four *Representative Concentration Pathways* (RCP) presented by the UN’s Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in 2014. These are called RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP6.0 and RCP8.5 and they reflect the concentration of the greenhouse gasses in the atmosphere for four future trajectories depending on humanity’s ability to reduce emissions. Data for each RCP was also collected for the Global Mean Surface Temperature Increase (GMSTI) and overall these pathways are strongly linked to climate change³.

3.2. Equipment

The prototype was developed in SuperCollider and the audio samples used for the sound design were downloaded from either Freesound⁴ or Sample Focus⁵ and then edited in Audacity⁶. Beyerdynamic DT 770 PRO headphones⁷ and a Focusrite Scarlett 2i2 audio interface⁸ were used during the user test.

³<https://www.ipcc.ch/assessment-report/ar5/>

⁴<https://freesound.org/>

⁵<https://samplefocus.com>

⁶<https://www.audacityteam.org/>

⁷<https://tinyurl.com/5d9maensl>

⁸<https://tinyurl.com/3c3u7jtz>

3.3. Stimuli design

3.3.1. Characteristic of the soundscapes

The creative process of the sound design was centered around two different soundscapes, each one representing the opposite polarity of the other. The *utopian* soundscape starts at the far left of the timeline in the year 1850, having the lowest data values and representing the relatively unspoiled climate before the second industrial revolution. The *dystopian* soundscape is supposed to represent the worst possible climate or “business as usual”-scenario, which was set for the future decade of 2100 at RCP8.5 with the highest data values. Since the aim for the prototype was to give the listener a moment to reflect on the state of the climate, and hopefully activate ST values, the soundscapes were created with the intention of invoking certain feelings on the behalf of the listener. Looking at the emotional 2D space of valence and activity [7], the emotions conveyed by the utopian soundscape are characterized by low activity and high valence (e.g. calmness, tenderness), while its dystopian counterpart renders emotions with low valence at higher activity (such as fear and anger). This emotional duality was chosen with the intent of creating a sense of decreasing balance to reflect the past state of the climate and possible future outcomes. With these two polarities representing the extreme ends of the spectrum, the in-between temporal soundscapes move between these fixed limits based on the data for each decade.

3.3.2. The Aesthetics

Since the aim of the sonification was to elicit certain feelings from the listener using musical qualities, the aesthetics became an important component of the sonification and a contributing factor to the creation of the sound design. This was to fully draw use of the emotional carrying abilities of music, for which the aesthetics play an important part. The aesthetics of the sonification draw inspiration from the composition *Lizard Point* from *Ambient 4: On Land* (1982) by Brian Eno, whose musical structure and use of timbres seemed fitting for the soundscapes of the study.

3.3.3. Mapping of Physical Dimensions

A mapping from the physical dimensions of the data to auditory dimensions was made (see detailed descriptions of mappings and acronyms in Table 2, based on Dubus and Bresin [8]). When the data did not have a given physical dimension, this was subjectively interpreted to an approximated category (e.g. GCP to size). Some of the data parameters have multiple suitable physical dimensions to be mapped to: this helps in conveying different aspects of the data while giving the resulting sound a more expressive character. One example is GSFC that is interpreted as the physical dimensions size and energy in order to both convey its increasing total amount as well as the active processes of production and usage. The auditory dimensions were then applied to certain parameters of the sound and manipulated in ways to fit its physical counterpart as well as the emotions associated with that particular soundscape (see Table 2, column 5).

In some instances, data parameters had an important impact on each other that was necessary to clarify sonically in the soundscape. In those cases, the values of a certain data parameter affected the sound of another data parameter, additionally to affect-

Data Parameter [unit]	Physical Dimensions	Auditory Dimensions	Sound	Implementation of the Auditory Dimensions
GHP (Global Human Population)	size, energy	loudness, spectral power, duration, pitch, reverberation time, musical mode	FM sawtooth synthesizer with envelope	attack and release of envelope, reverb mix, amplitude of tremolo effect, cut off-frequency of low pass-filter, modular frequency and amplitude
GCP (Global Cattle Population)	size	pitch, loudness, duration, reverberation time*	a continuously looped sample of cowbells	sampling rate, sample amplitude, reverb mix
GLU (Global Land Use) [billion hectare]	event rate, mass	tempo, pitch, instrumentation*, reverberation time*	drum kit	sampling rate, reverb mix, change from sample library from softly to aggressively played drums
GSFC (Global Synthetic Fertilizer Consumption) [ton]	energy, size	duration, spectral power, musical articulation*, reverberation time*	digitally synthesized noise	attack and release of envelope, cut off-frequency of low pass-filter, amplitude, reverb mix, amplitude of resonance frequencies
GMSL (Global Mean Sea Level Rise) [mm]	size	pitch, loudness, duration, spatialization*, temporal playback direction (forward, backwards)	a recording of seagulls calling with amplitude envelope	attack and release of envelope, amplitude
GMSTI (Global Mean Surface Temperature Increase)	temperature	pitch, musical harmonic structure*	a continuously played FM sine wave synthesizer-pad	modular frequency and amplitude
CO ₂ - carbon dioxide [ppm]	mass, size	duration, pitch, loudness, harmonic structure (in combination with other gasses)*	a sample of a female voice singing the vowel /u/	amplitude, sampling rate according to MIDI ratio
CH ₄ – methane [ppb]	mass, size	harmonic structure (in combination with other gasses)*	a sample of a female voice singing the vowel /u/	amplitude, sampling rate according to MIDI ratio
N ₂ O – nitrous oxide [ppb]	mass, size	harmonic structure (in combination with other gasses)*	a sample of a female voice singing the vowel /u/	amplitude, sampling rate according to MIDI ratio

Table 2: Mapping from data parameters to physical to auditory dimensions, sound and acoustic implementation (* = not an auditory dimension of Dubus and Bresin [8], but according to the emotional expression of the music or an subjective interpretation of the auditory dimension according to the nature of the data.).

ing the auditory dimensions of its own assigned sound (see 3.3.4). This was also made in order to create a stronger difference in the sound of the four different RCP trajectories. This method was used to strengthen the dependence between GCP and CH₄, where rising CH₄ values also increased the reverberation time and loudness of the cow bells sounds, in order to further enhance the perceived size of the space the sound is inhabiting and make it render more of an eerie feeling. The sound level of the bass melody of the GHP-data also increased with the rising temperature-data, in order to further establish the direct human impact of the rising temperature.

3.3.4. The Design of and Mapping of Sounds

A specific sound was mapped to each data parameter (see Table 2, column 4). This relationship could be ecological, e.g. GMSL mapped to the sound of a flock of seagulls. The mapping could also be based on a musical abstraction, a technique used when it seemed more suitable for the aesthetics of the soundscape as well

as more effectively conveying the physical dimension of the data according to the musical context. One example of this is the mapping of the data parameter GLU to a drum kit, because of its aggressive connotation of *hitting to chopping trees*, which then could be mapped to the physical dimension of event rate and the auditory dimension of tempo. The choice of sound could also be based on the acoustic relation to the other sounds already selected, e.g. in the case of an low frequent loud sound, such as the case of global population, the spectral centroid of the following sounds would not reside in the same frequency range in order to avoid interference and masking. At times the sound was selected according to its physical dimension, e.g. temperature according to Dubus and Bresin [8] most commonly mapped to pitch, hence a frequency modulator (FM) synth-pad was used as a representation of GMSTI, since it has a clear pitch, making a pitch shift easily detectable. Some sounds, based on their common category, were grouped together by having an identical timbre, but mapped in different ways, in order to show their common physical nature. As

the three greenhouse gasses CO₂, N₂O and CH₄, for which the same singing-sample was used to represent each of them. Thus, by mapping their pitch in different ways according to the physical dimension of size, they together create a choir singing in different harmonics.

Both synthesized and sampled sounds were used in the sound design. Sound samples were used for representing GCP (cow bells), GLU (drum kit), GMSL (the seagulls) and the greenhouse gasses (the choir). The rest were digitally synthesized in SuperCollider, being a FM sine wave-synth, FM sawtooth wave-synth and a filtered white noise generator. The FM synths were used because of their expressive ability to create both stable harmonic sounds as well as unstable noisy sounds within small changes of its modulator parameters, making it suitable for switching between the feelings associated with utopian soundscape as well as the dystopian one. The noise generator generates low-pass filtered white noise, with a similar spectral slope to that of pink noise, in the utopian soundscape. The envelope has a slow soft attack and release of its envelope and resonates in the harmonic frequencies of the key of the GMSTI synth-pad. Pink noise has shown in studies to have a calming psychological effect and facilitate sleeping [9], hence it's used in the utopian soundscape with the aim of further inducing the low activity high valence type of emotions. In the dystopian counterpart the low-pass filter disappears, replaced with the generation of white noise with shorter attack and release at non-periodic intervals, to create a harsher, more aggressive sound.

3.3.5. Musical Qualities of the Mapping

The expressive manipulation of musical parameters is a powerful tool to create an emotional connection with the listener. As mentioned in 3.3.1, the utopian and dystopian soundscapes aimed to convey opposite emotions, the utopian landscape inducing feelings of low activity and high valence (calmness, tenderness), while the dystopian is conveying feelings of higher activity and low valence (fear, anger). Based on the results mentioned in 2.2, these emotional dualities guided the timbre design of the sounds as well as the limits of the auditory parameters according to the different polarities. An example of this is the use of tempo-mapping of the drum kit of the GLU-data. In the utopian soundscapes the drums are barely noticeable, playing softly at an considerably slow pace in pseudo-periodic intervals. This is supposed to render feelings at low activity and high valence. In the dystopian soundscape the drum kit is instead played loudly at a higher tempo in longer non-periodic sequences, appearing unexpectedly in time. This loud chaotic behavior is used to stir high activity and low valence emotions.

Different musical modes are also used to communicate certain emotions to the listener. The positive feelings often associated with the Ionian mode, or major scale, fits the emotional spectrum of the utopian soundscape. This is applied for the harmonic instruments: the ascending bass melody of the GHP and the chord of the choir of the greenhouse gasses. In the dystopian soundscape the mode changes to Aeolian (the minor scale), playing a new descending melody. The chord of the choir also changes into a minor chord. This new mode is more associated with negative feelings, which is further enhanced with the downward movements of the melody. Another harmonic component in the soundscape is the synth-pad of the GMSTI-data, which is being played continuously. It plays two notes in a perfect fifth interval to the root note, which exists in both the Aeolian and Ionian mode, in order not to interfere

with the other harmonic components. The frequency of the fifth note's modulation frequency is mapped to the temperature data, making it oscillate at a high frequency in the dystopian soundscape, resembling an alarm. This can be considered a metaphor for a state of urgency, as an alarm of danger or a wake-up call.

Other filters and sound effects were also used to enhance the emotions of the two different soundscapes. Reverberation time and panning were applied to both create a sense of space as well as enhancing the unpleasant characteristics of some of the dystopian sounds.

3.3.6. The Breaking Point at 2020

When the timeline reaches the breaking point of our current decade, four different future climate scenarios are possible to explore, based on the different end polarities of the mapping. The RCP at 8.5, being the worst possible outcome, is represented by the dystopian soundscape and the other three alternatives sounding less dystopian at varying degrees. This works as an analogy for that we can't change the past but we have the power of changing the outcome of the future.

This breaking point becomes a natural way of making necessary discrete changes in some of the mappings. Some parameters were deemed not suited to be gradually changing, instead a distinct shift is made at that moment in time for some of the mappings, such as the change of drum kit from soft to loud of the GLU-data and the mode change of the bass melody of the GHP-data. This sudden change is also made to enhance the sense of urgency, that we're at a crossroad and the state of the climate depends on which road we choose.

3.4. Procedure

3.4.1. Participants

15 participants (7 M, 8 F) were recruited for the user test, with age between 21 and 42 (average age 25.93, SD=5.22). 13 of the participants were Swedish, 1 Icelandic/American and 1 Danish, none suffering from any kind of hearing impairment. The participants were divided into a test group of 9 persons and a control group of 6 persons, where the user test of the test group consisted of two listening tests, a pre-interview, interacting with the prototype and a post-interview, while the control group only did the interviews and the interaction with the prototype. The division into two groups was made to see if the listening tests, consisting of audio samples from the prototype, would somehow train the test group to a better understanding of the sonification prior to interacting with it.

3.4.2. Listening Test 1 & 2

The survey and the stimuli of listening test 1 and 2, ordered according to the order of the test, can be accessed online.⁹ The listening tests were conducted in a quiet room with only one participant and the experimenter present at a time. Both listening tests were taken using a Google form-survey. Before starting the test each participant was given a GDPR-consent form to approve followed by sharing some personal information: participant code, age, gender and if they suffer from any hearing impairments. They were also asked to answer to what degree they agree, according to a Likert scale from 1 ("strongly disagree") to 7 ("strongly agree"), to the

⁹<https://zenodo.org/record/6789179#.Yr9kEuxBw1I>

following statements: *I consider myself aware and knowledgeable concerning climate related issues* and *I consider myself an active proponent for sustainability*. These questions were asked to get an understanding of the participants' knowledge of and engagement in climate related issues.

The purpose of listening test 1 was to see if the mapping of physical dimensions to auditory dimensions and their acoustic implementation and choice of polarity was intuitive for the listener. This would hopefully give an indication if the sonification was successful in representing the data and the change in the physical domain it is supposed to embody. The sounds chosen for the test represented data parameters unmoved by the change in RCP values; GLU, GMSTI and GCP. The latter two are played constantly in the soundscape, hence being strong indicators of change in the data. The physical dimensions mapped to these data parameters are *event rate and mass*, *size* and *temperature*, which then, according to [8], were mapped to their respective auditory dimensions (see Table 2). Both a decrease and increase of each auditory dimension were recorded, creating 3x2 different sounds in total. The increase and decrease of the auditory dimensions of GMSTI and GCP was implemented using exponential envelopes, in order to make the change in the sound distinct. The time duration of both increase and decrease for both of these data parameters were set to 20 s. For the GLU-sound it was more convenient to use the original data steering the change in sound, which has a natural increase and decrease, instead of implementing an exponential envelope, making the time durations longer (around 50 s) than for the sounds of GMSTI and GCP.

The test started with the participant being provided written instructions of the test which consisted of six questions in total (one for each increasing and decreasing version of the three sounds), all in the following manner: *The following sound represents size. Listening to the sound, do you consider the size. . .*, with one of the physical dimensions in focus (size, temperature or the pair event rate and mass). When ready, the sound was played followed by the participant selecting one of the three alternatives: *decreasing, increasing or unchanged*. No unchanged version of the sounds were recorded, making the possible answer *unchanged* a way of telling if no change is perceived. Participants were allowed to listen to the sound as many times as they wanted to before moving on to the next question, but not allowed to listen to a previous sound or change the answer of a previous question. The order of the questions according to data parameters was randomized as well as the order of the answer alternatives for each question.

When listening test 1 was finished, participants continued with listening test 2. The goal with the second test was to see if the listener was able to hear the difference in emotions communicated by smaller nuanced changes between two different soundscapes, with the purpose of investigating if the sound design was successful in representing the emotional aspects of the data it was supposed to convey. The four different RCP soundscapes at year 2100 were chosen for the test, with them being clear indicators of different degrees of positive- and negativeness. RCP2.6 should sound the least negative, while RCP4.5, RCP6 and RCP8.5 should sound increasingly negative. A recording of an excerpt of each soundscape was made, making up 4 different recordings in total. The time duration was limited to 10 s, in order to facilitate comparison between them.

Listening test 2 began with participants reading the written instructions. For each question, with its corresponding pair of RCP soundscapes, the two sounds were played in sequence on the par-

icipant's command, upon which they selected one of them according to the following criterion: *Which of the following sounds do you consider the least positive?* There were a total of six questions. The playback order according to RCP values was randomized for each question. As in listening test 1, participants were allowed to listen to the sound as many times as they wanted to before moving on to the next question, but not allowed to listen to a previous sound or change the answer of a previous question.

3.4.3. Test 3: Prototype Interviews

In the third and final test, all participants were interviewed in two parts. The interview was semi-structured, with some questions always being asked (if time allowed) and the interviewer followed up some statements with further questions to help the interviewee dig deeper. The questions and instructions are available online⁹. The test started with them being read instructions which was followed by the first couple of questions. These required some reflection to answer as a warm-up, but they were unrelated to the study. They were then asked to share their thoughts on climate change. Since the purpose of the study is not to educate the participants on this topic but to help them reflect, this was done in order to prime them towards a desired state of mind before moving on to the prototype.

Afterwards, they received new instructions where they were told to listen to the prototype for at least five minutes or until told to stop, and that during this time they should reflect on the impact of climate change on nature, animals and people. The latter was important since it was found in a small pilot user study that participants were prone to focus on the sounds and what they represented instead of actually reflecting if left uninstructed. They were also encouraged to explore the different years at their own pace, which they could do by interacting with the slider that made out the prototype's timeline, and to interact with the button that changes the RCP.

When they were finished listening, the second part of the interview was conducted. Here they got to answer open-ended questions about their experience, for instance: what they had thought about while listening, what they had felt and if there were any sounds that had caught their attention. The goal was to get an image of how their thoughts had been influenced by the soundscape and whether the prototype had helped them foster deeper reflections. Therefore only the second part of the interview was evaluated, where all interviews where transcribed and all participants' responses were analyzed according to a number of common themes that emerged from the data. Also, since it is difficult to determine whether a reflection could have arisen even without the use of the prototype, all themes considered among the interview responses were related to the prototype and the sounds in some way.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Results: Listening Test 1 & 2

To the introductory questions *I consider myself aware and knowledgeable concerning climate related issues* the participants gave a mean score between 1 and 7 of 5.01 (SD=0.96) and to *I consider myself an active proponent for sustainability* a mean score of 5.01 (SD=1.44). As for listening test 1, a majority of the participants chose the correct alternative (i.e. correct as in the one corresponding with the intended mapping), as seen in the upper

Figure 1: Results listening test 1 and 2: The distribution of answers for all participants for each question corresponding to the given answer alternatives for listening test 1 (above) and 2 (below).

plot in Figure 1, with the highest score being 9 out of 9 for the sound of decreasing temperature, while the sound of increasing size had the lowest recognition rate (5 out of 9). Looking at the total number of correct answers for each person and each question (i.e. 9 persons x 6 questions = 54 possible answers), it's 43 out of 54, corresponding $\approx 80\%$ ($SD=0.21$). The mean of correct answers per participant (where 6 is the highest possible score) was 4.78 ($SD=1.30$). The results of listening test 2, with the amount of correct answers for all participants for each question, are presented in the lower plot in Figure 1. The total number of correct answers for all participants is 33 of 54, $\approx 61\%$ ($SD=0.14$), with the highest score being 8 out of 9 for question 5 (RCP6 and RCP8.5) and the lowest being for question 1 (RCP8.5 and RCP4.5). The mean of correct answers per participant is 3.67 ($SD=0.87$), with the highest possible score being 6.

4.2. Results: Prototype Interviews

The average listening time was 8 m and 48 s ($SD=2m\ 34s$), where the shortest was 5 m and the longest was 13 m and 17 s. All participants interacted with the prototype in different ways, but a frequent pattern was to initially slowly adjust the slider in a chronological order using the computer's trackpad until reaching the year 2100, to then doing larger leaps between years while interacting with the RCP button. The different themes found in the interviews in Test 3 are organized in the sub-sections below, typically for-

mulated as a number of participants that responded something in common. Each participant was anonymized and associated to a code throughout the analysis, e.g. A2 was the second participant of day A. From the analysis of the results it became clear that there is seemingly no difference in the quality of the responses between the two groups, meaning the impact of doing the listening tests beforehand are negligible and there are other factors such as the participant's previous experience of related topics that potentially plays a larger role. For this reason, the two groups were evaluated together.

4.2.1. From the Utopian to the Dystopian Soundscape

13 out of the 15 participants associated the utopian 1850 soundscape with more positive sentiments compared to the dystopian 2100 soundscape, describing it as e.g. calm (A1, A2, B3) and pleasant (B10), while the latter soundscape was described as e.g. dark (A5, B8, B10) and scary (A3, B7, B9). The remaining two participants either did not explicitly state any sentiments (B5) or believed that it sounded the saddest in the 1990s and that the future years sounded more hopeful (B2). Furthermore, all participants brought up reflections related to how the sounds changed when they navigated through the years in the prototype, ranging from simpler descriptions of sentiment variations to sharing mental images, and 13 of these did at some point relate their timeline interactions, and what they heard, to climate change. As participant A5 put it:

"It sounded like there was a buildup until 2030 and then things fell apart. And then I got the image in my head that it's probably going to be like that with the climate also."

4.2.2. Urgency

Eight of the 15 participants expressed that the prototype conveyed, in different ways, a sense of urgency or that humanity is running out of time, which participant A1 described in the following quote:

"These big sounds make you feel like something big is happening, like something you cannot control, and that will be like our situation within a few years. That we cannot control it anymore. It's gone way off. Like the global warming has gone to a point where we cannot stop it anymore and things are just going crazy, and that is scary."

4.2.3. Emotional engagement

Six participants brought up and reflected on how the prototype was able to elicit feelings in a different way compared to solely reasoning or reading about climate change. Two of them expressed that listening to the soundscape helped them gain a feel for an issue that oftentimes is too vast to emotionally grasp, while participant A5 compared it to music or art where it is often necessary to make use of your empathy to make sense of it.

4.2.4. Lack of Insight

Four participants brought up that they think the experience would have given them more if the listener was given information about the different sounds and the underlying data, where two potential benefits could be that it would make the prototype more relatable (A2) and that it would reduce confusion (B8). Participant A3 expressed that it would take the prototype one step further than the

typical doomsday narrative and thought it could provide more actionable takeaways:

“I get this data is really negative and yeah kind of like doomsday vibes but like: What is it actually presenting? I think that could be more helpful, to like: OK, what do we do about it? Where do we start?”

4.2.5. Final Thoughts

When asked if they felt like they had gotten anything out of the experience, all but one participant mentioned at least one thing – often accompanied by reflections. Among other things it was brought up that it was good to be reminded to ponder about climate change (A4, B3, B9, B10), that the interactive timeline allowed for swift comparisons between different years (A1, B6) and one participant (B8) solely stated that they got a bad conscience from their reflections.

The last question was about whether they think the prototype could be used to increase an individual’s concern for the climate or boost their motivation to live more sustainably. Due to time constraints, two participants were not asked this question, but the remaining 13 were positive towards the idea. They did however come up with various suggestions on where it would fit and how it could be improved. One suggestion was to somehow scale it up, either by displaying the soundscape in an audio-only cinema setting (B2), by making it part of a large scale exhibition (B3) or by experiencing it with others to be able to debrief afterwards (A3).

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. Listening Test 1 & 2

As for the limitations of the listening tests, the small number of participants make it hard to draw any general conclusions considering the perception of the mappings and the soundscapes tested. They can only be viewed as possible indications of certain trends within this particular sample group of users, not as statistically significant results. Hence mean and standard deviation values are solely used with the purpose of describing the general traits of the data. Another aspect worth mentioning is that the isolated renditions of these sounds differ from the sonic context in which they appear in the soundscape, which likely change the perception of them. The tests does neither cover all mappings or all possible soundscapes, hence only taking the examples used for the stimuli in regard.

The results of listening test 1 seems to favour the intended mappings of the physical dimensions, with the majority of the participants choosing the correct answer for each question. Looking at Figure 1, the scores of the latter three sounds, being the second appearance of each physical dimension, is higher than those of the first three. This could indicate that most of the participants implicitly learned to understand the mapping through training after prior exposure, as mentioned by Hermann et al [10], adapting their listening according to the given context of the sounds that they previously listened to. Looking at the mean of the mean scores for each of the first three questions for each participant in comparison to that of the last three questions, we can also see an increase from 0.52 (SD=0.18) to 0.70 (SD=0.20). Going into some details of the results, 9 out of 9 participants answered correctly to the question of decreasing temperature and 8 out of 9 for the increasing temperature, implying that this mapping seemed intuitive

to a majority of the participants. With the sound being a synth pad based on sine waves with changing harmonics, it has a clear pitch for which a change could be perceived as quite noticeable. For the physical dimensions of size, only 5 out of 9 perceived the change as increasing, being the lowest score of all sounds with 3 participants instead considering it decreasing and 1 unchanged. Interestingly enough these participants later choose the same answer for the sound of decreasing size, which could mean that they changed their mind about the sound with a point of reference or answered at random. For the event rate and mass, the participants also scored a bit lower the first time they listened to the sound (6 out of 9), with 2 participants considering it unchanged and 1 increasing instead of decreasing. This could be as a consequence of it being 30 s longer than the other sounds, following the GLU-data instead of an exponential envelope as for the other physical dimensions of the listening test. Even though data have a quite noticeable change from lower to higher values, its long time duration could make it less noticeable and not as a clearly perceived change. The mapping also differs a bit from how it is presented in the soundscapes, where the pauses between appearances can range between 30 to 60 s, with pauses decreasing with increasing temporal GLU-values. This time range was considerably decreased for the sake of limiting the time duration of the sample used in the test. Even though this alteration in the mapping could possibly change the perception of the sounds, the version in the test still gives a rough estimate for the intuitiveness of the mapping of the physical dimensions of event rate and mass to the loudness and instrumentation of the drum kit.

Listening test 2 did not have a majority of correct answers for each question, as seen in Figure 1, with the lowest score being the first question, where the correct answer was chosen 2 out of 9. Still some questions received quite high scores, but considering the mean for the correct answers per question 5.5 (SD=2.26), it is quite close to the randomly chosen 4.5 correct answers, especially within the high variance of 2.26. The reason for the poor scoring could partly be explained by the variability of the instrumentation of each recorded soundscape, all of them being randomly generated according to the mapping and the data. The soundscapes used as stimuli were excerpts from longer recordings, each selected at a moment in time where each of them had similar instrumentation but still sounding different depending on their RCP value. This resulted in some variation, e.g. some soundscapes starting with a transient hit while others didn’t, which could affect the perception outside the influence of the difference in RCP-data. Another potential source for the low scores and bias could be the randomization of the soundscapes, which at times seems to follow patterns, e.g. for the majority of the questions the correct answer is played as the second sound and the RCP4.5-soundscape is played second 3 times in a row. When listening to and comparing the 4 different soundscapes, it’s quite hard to tell them apart, which also might have affected the results. Since the soundscapes are generated through sonification, the final outcome can’t be controlled; it is the data speaking according to the mapping of it. Unfortunately the future of the climate looks quite bleak, just as the soundscapes at 2100 sound. With the best worst outcome at RCP2.6 still sounding quite dystopian, the listener might reflect over the reality of no bright future but rather a less dark one. Even though this being the case, the mapping should reflect the worst results at RCP8.5 sounding noticeably worse, same goes for RCP4.5 and RCP6. The sounds that have more of a detectable difference between small changes in the data are the ones representing GMSTI and GCP,

with them being played constantly in the soundscape. For the occasionally played transient sounds, e.g. the greenhouse gases, GSFC and GHP, a change in data might not be perceived as clear. A fine tuning of these mappings might lead to higher contrasts between the soundscapes in emotional expression in the range of negative and positive. For future listening tests on the subject, using stimuli with the same instrumentation for each soundscape and only data dependent differences could possibly give more conclusive results. Even though the results from listening test 2 seem inconclusive, the results of the interviews indeed indicate that a majority of participants, after having interacted with the prototype, recognized the communicated emotions (see 4.2.1). Hence it seems as at least the core emotions of the two polarities were successfully communicated.

5.2. General Thoughts Concerning the Design

Looking more generally at aspects potentially having a negative effect on the results of both the listening tests, the interpretations of the data parameters' physical dimensions at times seemed a bit far fetched and non-intuitive. Even though the results of Dubus and Bresin [8] are quite extensive, some physical dimensions were hard to match to the data used in this study. This sometimes lead to subjective judgements, e.g. interpreting GCP as size instead of amount, which should be investigated closer in a user test in order to determine their validity. In the manner that this study has balanced between art and science, it is sometimes hard to judge if it tilts too much in favor of the artistic for being a scientific study. But, as mentioned by Vickers [5], it is also important to keep in mind that the strict separation between sonification and musical compositions is not necessarily meaningful, especially when trying to connect with the emotions of the listener.

5.3. Did the Prototype Facilitate Reflection?

The results in 4.2.1 indicate that the prototype was successful in eliciting the emotions it was designed to communicate and that it in many cases gave rise to, potentially new and unsought, thoughts and reflections about climate change. To some extent, this is confirmed as well by the results reported in 4.2.3 where participants appreciated the sound's capability of conveying emotions. Also, as seen in 4.2.2, a majority of the participants brought up that they experienced a sense of urgency when interacting with the prototype. This, together with the generally positive responses listed in 4.2.5 and that four participants expressed that it was good to be given the opportunity to reflect on climate change, suggest that the prototype has impacted the participants' reflections, although it is still uncertain to what degree they have been aided by listening to and interacting with it.

6. FUTURE STUDIES

It could be relevant to evaluate the prototype in the context of values. Even though the interviews contain reflections that could be linked to different ST values, e.g. protecting the environment, deeper insights could be harvested if the participants values were mapped before and after the study, perhaps for a prolonged study period where they get to listen everyday for a certain duration.

As seen in 4.2.4 and 4.2.5, the participants shared their ideas on things to try out. Interestingly, one of the participants suggested a potential future study, that would not require any changes to the

prototype, consisting in conducting user tests on groups of people and letting them discuss their experience afterwards. The conversations could potentially yield deeper reflections and it would be of relevance to see if the participants find the experience more fulfilling as a whole.

Another interesting development of the study could be to run further listening tests, for example by letting participants to set the values of different sound parameters used in the design of the soundscapes in order to identify how their polarities vary between different scenarios [11].

7. CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this study was to see whether sonification producing soundscapes with musical aesthetics could help listeners in reflecting on the impact of climate change and the current state of the planet. To this end, an interactive prototype was developed and a user study with 15 participants was conducted which consisted of two listening tests and a prototype exploration session combined with an interview. The user study indicated that the sound design and sonification resonated with the listeners and elicited the emotions they were designed to communicate, while at the same time affecting their reflections. It does however remain uncertain to what extent they were helped by the prototype while reflecting. For future studies it could be relevant to investigate how the participants values are affected or to conduct a user study with multiple participants simultaneously to take part of reflections that emerge in group discussions.

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